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FLEXURAL BEHAVIOR OF FOAM CORED SANDWICH STRUCTURES WITH THROUGH-THICKNESS REINFORCEMENTS

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#ICCM22

The project

Desire to continuously improve performances by exploring and investigating cutting-edge materials, manufacturing processes and numerical techniques.

Experimental Methods and Finite Element Modelling

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Three point bending tests on sandwich panels with three different configurations.

Aim: Investigate the different failure modes and the benefits of using through-thickness reinforcements.

2L [mm]	200
S [mm]	150
B [mm]	75
h_c [mm]	15
h_f [mm]	2.7

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

- Skin: ABQ_PLY_FABRIC material model.
- Core: Crushable foam material model + foam failure criterion based on the invariant theory.
- Failure of the skin-core interface modelled as foam failure rather than interfacial failure (techniques as CZM and VCCT were assessed and found to have limitations).

Aim: Validation of the numerical approach.

Results

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Configuration 1

Configuration 2

Configuration 3

FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING

